

Investment Decisions on Life Insurance Policy Among Public School Teachers

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Abstract: *The study aimed to identify the factors influencing the investment decisions of public school teachers' life insurance policies in Claver, Surigao del Norte. A quantitative – descriptive survey design was utilized using mean and standard deviation, frequency count and percentage, and analysis of variance. The teachers' profile was the study's independent variable, and its indicators were age, sex, rank position, civil status, and years in service. While the influencing factors such as premium offered, company image, service quality, satisfaction level, and company-client relationship served as the dependent variable. The findings indicate no significant relationship between the influencing factors and the profile variables. The paper recommends that the insurance companies propose new strategies to increase investment through the use of the technology and improve the company's service quality. In addition, school administrators should work with stakeholders in conducting financial literacy programs on insurance investment for the teachers to aid more knowledge in expenses management and future security.*

Keywords: Premium, Company Image, Service Quality, Satisfaction Level, Company-Client Relationship

I. INTRODUCTION

Human life is the most important asset, and life insurance is an important type of insurance that provides financial protection to a person and his family at uncertain risks or damage. It provides safety and protection to individuals and encourages savings among people (Stojakovic, A., & Jeremic, L., (2016).

Increased consumer knowledge regarding life insurance during the COVID-19 epidemic, according to S&P Global Market Intelligence (2021), may have played a crucial role in raising sales in the first quarter of 2021. Total life premiums totaled \$48.93 billion in the first quarter, up 8.1 percent over the previous year's quarter. Individual life premiums increased by 9.0 percent in the first quarter of 2020, while group life premiums increased by 5.1 percent. Many consumers are more likely to get life insurance due to the pandemic; nearly one-third (31%) believe they are more likely to do so due to the pandemic (Wood, S., Leyes, M., & Scanlon, J. T., 2021).

In recent years, the Philippine life insurance industry has experienced significant growth. With the advent of banks, mutual funds, and financial institutions offering a diverse range of financial security products, the sector is expected to grow even more. Employee benefits, particularly health insurance packages, are in high demand as businesses grow. During the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, the Philippines' customers' perspectives on insurance shifted because of the uncertainty and reduced economic activity. This situation and the availability of newer insurance coverage for individuals with pre-existing medical conditions resulted in a minor increase of 1.67 percent in insurance penetration in the Philippines compared to 2019 (Statista Research Department, 2022).

Educators make up a large percentage of the profession and play an important role in developing nations. They do, however, have the lowest personal insurance percentage, given that they are also on the front line in the present pandemic that the world is experiencing. However, the study focused on those teachers who invested in life insurance policies on top of the government-mandated insurance, which also provides retirement and life insurance plans.

In a pre-interview conducted, a primary school teacher noted that teachers invest in life insurance policies to ensure their future. It provides safety and protection to their family and encourages savings among people. Life insurance can be used for their children's education, hospital expenses, and retirement fund. Another public-school teacher said that age could affect the premium one must pay. It is expensive if the insurer is old. Life insurance is most affordable if you are young and healthy because your premiums are determined by your medical profile, family medical history, and age (Personal Interview, December 19, 2021).

These encouraged the researcher to study the factors influencing the teachers' investment decisions on life insurance policies, what they consider investing in, their most preferred life insurance type, and the significant difference of the influencing factors when grouped by their profile variables. Moreover, it is for the researcher to provide information to the community that will guide them when availing of life insurance, especially for those who do not have a background in life insurance.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter discusses the theories, facts, and concepts of various authors of this study to provide a frame of reference to support the study.

2.1 Life Insurance Policy

Life insurance has been a crucial component of estate planning. It can provide a death payout that is tax-free and far exceeds the premiums paid. It is built on the principles of risk pooling and the law of large numbers (Gallo, J. J., 1999). A contract with an insurance company defines a life insurance policy. The insurance company gives recipients a lump-sum payout for premium payments, known as a death benefit (Granovetter, M., & Swedberg, R., 2011). Life insurance is typically chosen depending on the owner's needs and intentions. Term life insurance, for example, protects you for a specific length of time, whereas permanent life insurance, such as whole and universal life, protects you for the rest of your life (Stout, 2019). It is important to note that death benefits from all types of life insurance are generally income tax-free (F. Dong et al., 2019).

There are many types of life insurance – whole life, term life, universal life, among others – and hundreds of insurance companies, each with unique requirements. However, there are two main life insurance policies: term life and whole life. Term life is a policy that covers you for a set period, typically 10, 15, 20, or 30 years. Once the policy expires, so does the coverage. Whole life policies provide permanent coverage that lasts a lifetime, premiums, and a guaranteed cash value (Stout, 2019).

2.1.1 Life Insurance Policy in the Philippines

The Philippine insurance industry is a developing and evolving market (Santos, 2013). However, the Philippines has the smallest insurance market among member countries of the ASEAN 5, despite having the second-largest population (Galolo, 2015). The Philippine life insurance industry has seen major growth in market size, penetration rates, and product range in recent years. As the country draws closer to full integration into the ASEAN Economic Community, new channels are opening – bancassurance, for example – and additional market entrants are expected. All of this is based on the Philippines' continued economic growth, with the industries that are driving it, such as business process outsourcing (BPO), also providing a lucrative platform for expansion in the life sector as businesses grow, demand for employee benefits rises, and health insurance packages are in high demand (Oxford Business Group, 2018).

2.2 Demographic Profile

Demographic risk is a serious threat to the financial stability of an insurance company having underwritten life insurance and annuity business (Gründl, H., 2006). Natural hedging opportunities are created by the inverse impact of changes in mortality regulations on the market value of life insurance (Gründl, Post, and Schulze, 2005). Investors' risk and return expectations depend upon various demographic factors and establish a relationship between demographic attributes like age, gender, the investor's spiritual orientation, and investment decision-making (Gakhar and Prakash, 2013).

Ganesan, S., Namasivayam, and Rajendran, S. (2006) reviewed the socio-economic variables responsible for acquiring life insurance policies and the policyholders' preference for company policies. It was discovered from the assessment that variables such as policyholders' age, academic level, and sex are irrelevant, but the amount of revenue, employment, and family are significant factors for the purchase of life insurance products (Nekmahmud Md et al., 2017). However, Thune (2018) noted that sex plays a significant role in life insurance premium costs. Generally speaking, rates for women are less expensive than they are for men since women tend to live longer. Women have a life expectancy at birth of 81.3, while it is 76.3 on average for men. That allows them to charge a lower premium.

2.3 Investment Decision Factors

There are many factors in developing consumers' perception of life insurance policies, such as consumer loyalty, service quality, satisfaction level, company image, and company-client relationship (Adhikari, P. R., 2020 & Epetimehin, F. M., 2011). Moreover, Tanmay et al. (2015) disclosed that consumers' purchase decisions depend on

quality, availability, type of business, suggestions, and service promptness. However, in the current study, five factors are considered and discussed below.

It was found that an investor in life insurance considers *premiums offered* and prefers to pay monthly and quarterly premiums (Tati, R. K., & Baltazar, E. B. B., 2018). Whole life insurance provides long-term objectives, consistent premiums to customers, and guaranteed cash value accumulation that covers you as long as you live (Mahajan, 2013). On the other hand, universal life insurance provides customers flexibility in their policy's premium payments, and you can change your premium payments; you can also boost or reduce your insurance face value (Dave, 2019). Zhang (2009) also indicates that an excellent *company image* has benefits such as attracting fresh clients, improving customer loyalty, making products simpler to sell, and thus increasing profit. Similar studies have shown that a strong corporate reputation could enforce client confidence and customer loyalty resulting in greater product demand (Wang, C. Y., 2010 & Okidarsyah, M., 2017). The company's image is considered one of the most important by customers when choosing an insurance company (Suneja, A. et al., 2009 & Shafeiha, S. et al., 2011).

Moreover, insurance penetration also depends on *service quality* (Panigrahi S. et al., 2018 & Krishnamurthy et al., 2005). This sector's future development and greater efficiencies in customer service will rely on how efficiently insurers meet their customers' expectations and requirements and will be able to alter consumers' perceptions and communicate what they have to give (Krishnamurthy et al., 2005; Rani, S.V., & Soni, A.K., 2019). Proper handling of client complaints, efficient mechanism for managing client grievances, and quick claim settlement procedures are some of how customer satisfaction can be improved (Siddiqui, M. H., & Sharma, T. G., 2010). Additionally, the life insurance industry study discovered that *satisfaction level* was favorably linked to the repurchase choices of the client (Nyaguthii, M. J., 2013). Satisfaction may emerge from product experience, vendor experience, and after-sales service. It may come from the insurer's expertise and services, and the insurer's relationship with the service provider may also impact his choice considerably (Yu, T.-W., & Tseng, L.-M., 2016). Satisfied customers are likely to stay loyal (a good relationship) and boast favorable behavioral intentions toward the company (Pappas et al., 2014). On the other hand, a disappointed consumer is unlikely to have a positive relationship with a company (Roberts et al., 2003).

Finally, many available services helped organizations boost client interaction. Thus, today's need is effective and automated customer interaction management for a good *company-client relationship* (Anshari et al., 2019). The organization must also evaluate client information to reveal customer behavior patterns and comprehend their customers' real value (Kumar, V., & Reinartz, W., 2018). Its achievement must be analyzed client interactions from a lifetime view (Raab, G. et al., 2016). The insurance industry must focus on building healthy customer relationships as important attributes when choosing a life insurance policy (Chaudhary, S., 2016).

2.4 Investment Decisions on Life Insurance Policy

Muthukumar and Rajesh (2014) identified the important role of life insurance both in individual lives and in society. Many factors affect customers' investment decisions in life insurance. According to Tati & Baltazar (2018), the overall perception of investors toward life insurance is found to be positive. The majority of the customers feel insurance is a tax-saving option than risk protection and should be a multi-faceted investment option.

2.5 Conceptual Framework

This study is anchored on Zietz (2003) and Jain (2018), which state that specific demographic and economic factors may be identifiable as traits influencing the investment decisions for life insurance and discusses the general environmental issues related to life insurance demand. Moreover, Adhikari (2020) and Epetimehin (2011) consider the factors such as service quality, satisfaction level, company image, and company-client relationship consumers' may depend on in making investment decisions.

In this study, the demographic profile serves as the independent variable with age, sex, rank or position, civil status, and years in services as indicators. Moreover, the investment decision factors serve as the dependent variables with premium offered, company image, service quality, satisfaction level, and company-client relationship as study indicators. These concepts are relevant to the present study because they will be used as a basis for the decision-making process of potential investors in the life insurance policy. Thus, it will provide information to the life insurance companies in developing marketing activities tailored to their market demand.

As shown in Figure 1, identifying the profile and factors influencing the customers' investment decisions will better understand the life insurance policy the market needs.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of factors influencing investment decisions on life insurance policy

III. METHOD

3.1 Research Design

In this study, a quantitative descriptive survey research design was used to determine the degree of influence of the investment decision factors on the life insurance policy investment of the teachers. According to McCombes, S. (2019), a descriptive research method is to define a population, condition, or phenomenon correctly and systematically. It is suitable when the study aims to define features, frequencies, trends, correlations, and categories.

3.2 Research Participants

The study was conducted in the Claver District of Surigao del Norte, Philippines. It consisted of eighteen (18) public schools, sixteen (16) elementary schools, and two (2) high schools with 331 total teachers. Only ninety-one (91) have invested in a life insurance policy, which was considered the study's population. Furthermore, using sloven's formula, 74 public school teachers were considered the sample respondents.

3.2 Sampling Technique

The study used non-probability, purposive sampling. It was purposive because only the public school teachers assigned in Claver District who invested in life insurance policies were considered respondents of the study. According to Ben Foley (2018), purposive sampling, also known as selective sampling, is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in their study. This sampling method requires researchers to have prior knowledge about the purpose of their studies to choose and approach eligible participants properly.

3.3 Content Validity and Reliability

After completing the pilot survey, the data were analyzed using SPSS. Before distributing the questionnaires, the draft was initially submitted to the adviser and experts and the typical respondents for face and content validity. Reliability refers to an assessment tool's degree in producing consistent and stable results. The study yielded a 0.854 Cronbach alpha, indicating that the instrument was reliable. Commonly, Cronbach alpha is used to measure the internal consistency; that is, how closely related a set of items are as a group. It is most commonly used when a Likert-type scale is adopted in the questionnaire to determine whether the scale is reliable or not. The study used the suggested above 0.6 coefficient value (Babin et al., 2010).

On the other hand, content validity was established to ensure the instruments' validity (Cozby, 1977) from the pretest and re-test method done before the actual research. The research instrument sought experts' opinions in the study and peer review. This activity facilitated the necessary revision and modification of the research instrument, thereby enhancing validity. Borg and Gall (1985) point out that an instrument's validity is improved through expert judgment.

3.4 Data Gathering and Analysis

A letter of approval to the district supervisors and principals of the surveyed teachers was accomplished, allowing them to participate in the study. The survey questionnaires were handed over to the participants, and they were requested to answer the questionnaire. To ensure the proper accomplishment of the questionnaire, the researchers explained the purpose of the study to the respondents. The data gathered were classified, tabulated, and analyzed to answer the statements of the problem. Data collected were analyzed using statistical packages presented in tables. The statistical package used in analyzing the data gathered from the field was Microsoft Excel (2016 edition) and SPSS statistical packages with AMOS. The data analysis used frequency count and percentage distribution to represent the average rating as to the profile of the respondents. At the same time, the mean and standard deviation was applied to determine the influence of the investment decision factors on the respondents. On the other hand, analysis of

variance was used to determine the significant difference between the investment decision factors when grouped according to their profile variables. These analysis techniques were chosen after careful consideration of renowned researchers' various methods in the field from existing literature (Rooij, Lusardi & Alessie, 2009; Lusardi & Mitchell, 2005).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Demographic profile

Table 1 shows that most life insurance policyholders are female teachers (74%) and from 24 – 30 years old (42%). It is also indicated that most of them are new in the teaching profession with about 2 – 5 years in service with a rank position of Teacher 1 (39%). This means that younger teachers are the common life insurance investors. Despite being new in teaching, most of them are already married, completing 66% of the total number of respondents.

Table 1 - Profile of the Teacher-Respondents

	Demographic Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Age	24 - 30 years old	31	42
	31 - 37 years old	19	26
	38 - 44 years old	10	13
	45 years old and above	14	19
Sex	Male	19	26
	Female	55	74
Rank/Position	Teacher 1	29	39
	Teacher 2	17	23
	Teacher 3	19	26
	Others	9	12
Civil Status	Single	24	33
	Married	49	66
	Widowed	1	1
Years in Service	2 - 5 years	28	38
	6 - 9 years	17	23
	10 - 13 years	13	17
	14 years and above	16	22

4.2 Type of life insurance policy

Table 2 shows that most teachers invested in whole life insurance (65%), followed by term life insurance and universal life insurance policyholders covering 22% and 13%, respectively. The result indicates that most teachers have permanent life insurance; this specifies that the teacher prefers to invest in insurance with lifetime coverage. According to one of the respondents, whole life insurance is good because it is not just insurance but also an investment. Because of this insurance, your future and your family's future are also secured since it has cash value, and during an emergency, the insurance company will provide financial assistance.

Table 2- Preferred Life insurance Policy

Insurance Type	Frequency	Percentage
Term life Insurance	16	22
Whole Life Insurance	48	65
Universal Life Insurance	10	13

4.3 Influence of investment decision factors

Table 3 presents the degree of influence of Premium Offered as a factor for life insurance policy investment among teachers. As shown below, the company has a quick and high return of premium rate resulting in a "highly influential" interpretation and has the highest response mean of 3.20 and a standard deviation of 0.78. This means that

the respondents agreed that the premium rate has a high influence on their investment decisions, but standard deviation indicates quite different answers from one another. On the contrary, the company offers discounts on the premium offered has the lowest response mean of 2.76 with a standard deviation of 0.79, interpreted as "highly influential." It indicates that the respondents have to disperse and scatter answers regarding the company offering a discount on the premium.

Table 3 – Degree of Influence in terms of Premium Offered

Items Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
<i>I invested in life insurance because...</i>				
1. The company offers low premium	3.09	0.83	Agree	Highly Influential
2. The company has a quick and high return on premium	3.20	0.78	Agree	Highly Influential
3. The company provides an additional period after the due date to pay the premium	3.04	0.75	Agree	Highly Influential
4. The company offers discounts on the premiums offered	2.76	0.79	Agree	Highly Influential
5. The company offers a flexible premium rate	3.08	0.77	Agree	Highly Influential
Grand Mean	3.03	0.78	Agree	Highly Influential

Thus, the overall variable is still rated as "agree" and is interpreted as a "highly influential" degree of influence on investment decisions with a grand mean response of 3.03 and a standard deviation of 0.78. The results indicated that the teacher respondents' answers are scattered, meaning that most of the answers are different but have an average mean that is described as agreeing. Thus, most respondents prefer to purchase insurance wherein they control the premiums they have to pay.

The amount of premiums is dependent on what type of life insurance a customer is investing in. According to Jaramillo (2011), term life insurance is the most basic and usually the most affordable, while whole and universal have a much higher premium. Affordable premium plays an important role in building consumers' preferences towards one company for people looking for a less expensive life insurance policy.

Table 4 displays the degree of impact of Company Image as a factor for teachers' investment in a life insurance policy. Among the statements indicated above, the highest mean response of 3.47 and a standard deviation of 0.71 specified that the teachers prefer to invest in a company with a good reputation and is interpreted as "very highly influential" in the investment decision of the respondents. On the contrary, the cooperative and friendliness of the agents of the company response got the lowest mean of 3.26 with a standard deviation of 0.70, yet it is described as "strongly agree" and interpreted as "very highly influential." This indicates that the respondents have dispersed answers in considering the company's image of the cooperative and friendliness of agents as factors why teachers invest in life insurance.

Table 4 – Degree of Influence in terms of Company Image

Items Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
<i>I invested in life insurance because...</i>				
1. The company has a good reputation	3.47	0.71	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential
2. The company has cooperative and friendly agents	3.26	0.70	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential
3. The company gives value to its customers	3.35	0.67	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential
4. The company has a good relationship with customers	3.41	0.64	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential
5. The company is able to fulfill its duties and responsibilities to its customers	3.36	0.73	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential
Grand Mean	3.37	0.69	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential

As a result, the degree of influence of company image in investment decisions has a grand mean of 3.37 with a standard deviation of 0.69 interpreted as "very highly influential" in the respondents' investment choice. Hence the majority of the respondents look for a trusted company for insurance.

It can be inferred that trust is a very important factor that most customers look at before buying a policy. The company's goodwill attracts many people for a life insurance policy. It is relative to the study of Levin (2010), which states that customers consider attributes like the reputation of the company and referral as important when making such decisions and is an important variable to be considered before purchasing from the insurance company. These features are considered important by the customer as the life insurance products are quite comprehensive and can be customized as per the need of customers. Due to these features, this factor is connoted as the company's image.

Table 5 shows the degree of influence of Service Quality as a factor for life insurance policy investment among teachers. The highest mean response of 3.38 with a standard deviation of 0.66 indicated that the teachers invest in life insurance because of the proper guidance and immediate complaint handling, and is interpreted as "very highly influential." Nevertheless, the teachers prefer hassle-free settlement of purchasing life insurance, reaching a mean of 3.19 with a standard deviation of 0.63; though it is the lowest mean, the teacher finds it also influential as it is interpreted as "highly influential" in investing in life insurances.

Table 5 – Degree of Influence in terms of Service Quality

Items Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
<i>I invested in life insurance because...</i>				
1. It provides hassle free-settlements	3.19	0.63	Agree	Highly Influential
2. The agents are responsible for customers	3.20	0.72	Agree	Highly Influential
3. The agents respond promptly to inquiries	3.35	0.61	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential
4. They provide on-time services	3.24	0.66	Agree	Highly Influential
5. The company provides proper guidance and immediate complaint handling	3.38	0.66	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential
Grand Mean	3.27	0.66	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential

Thus, the grand mean of 3.27, described as "strongly agree," shows that the company's service quality towards the customer is interpreted as "very highly influential." This means that the company's quality of service is also a contributing factor that influences the respondent's investment choice.

The life insurance company must provide clients with timely error-free service. Faulty receipts, late insurance maturity, and wrongful premium amount are poor service quality. According to Ame (2013), staff must be sufficiently trained to provide error-free and timely service to clients. Negligence of any kind should be prevented as much as possible because this will result in an unsatisfied client who is not valued in any service industry. The life insurance company's staff and agents must also be knowledgeable in answering the customer's queries and numerous issues

Table 6 shows the degree of impact of satisfaction level as a factor for teachers' investment in a life insurance policy. Among the rating statements, the company providing solutions to customers' complaints has the highest mean response of 3.38 with a standard deviation of 0.73 and is interpreted as "very highly influential." On the contrary, the company providing satisfactory services has the lowest mean response of 3.23 with a standard deviation of 0.61, "highly influential." It also signifies that the respondents have different perspectives on the companies that provide satisfactory services to their customers.

Table 6 – Degree of Influence in terms of Satisfaction Level

Items Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
<i>I invested in life insurance because...</i>				
1. The agents display a pleasant attitude towards the customers	3.35	0.63	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential
2. The company provides satisfactory services	3.23	0.61	Agree	Highly Influential
3. The terms and conditions of the contract are properly	3.30	0.70	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential

explained to the customers					
4. I am satisfied with the relation of the company to its customers	3.28	0.65	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential	
5. The company provides solutions to customers' complaints	3.38	0.73	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential	
Grand Mean	3.31	0.66	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential	

Hence, the grand mean of 3.31 is described as "strongly agree" with a standard deviation of 0.66, interpreted as a "very highly influential" factor in an investment decision. This means that the ability of the company to satisfy their customers with their products and services has a very high influence on customers' investment choices.

The aspects of client satisfaction include over or under fulfillment rates and the sense of fair treatment. The views and perceptions of customers of a specific product and service may generate recognizable results from previous experiences. As Bidlani (2011) mentioned, customers expect companies to have an easy and seamless service delivery method to obtain reliable service. Then customer satisfaction becomes the complete evaluation of a customer's experience with a business, leading to customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction implies the impression of acceptable service.

Table 7 shows the influence of the Company-Client Relationship as a factor for life insurance policy investment among teachers. Among the rated statements, "the company gives value to its customers" has the highest mean response of 3.44, with a standard deviation of 0.60 described as a "very highly influential" factor. However, a proper reminder of installment has the lowest mean response of 3.20 with a standard deviation of 0.66; the data denotes that proper reminder of installment has dispersed and scattered answers. Despite being marked as the lowest mean, it is also considered influential in investing decisions in life insurance as it is interpreted as "highly influential."

Table 7 - Degree of Influence in terms of Company-Client Relationship

Items Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
<i>I invested in life insurance because...</i>				
1. The proper reminder of installments by agents.	3.20	0.66	Agree	Highly Influential
2. The company provides personal attention to every customer	3.24	0.72	Agree	Highly Influential
3. The company understands the customer's financial needs	3.38	0.70	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential
4. The agents are cooperative and entertaining	3.22	0.67	Agree	Highly Influential
5. The company gives value to its customers	3.44	0.60	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential
Grand Mean	3.30	0.67	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential

Thus, the variable's grand mean of 3.30, described as "strongly agree" with a standard deviation of 0.67, is "very highly influential." If the customers feel at ease and valued by the company, they will be more likely to stay in the company. This means that the way the company treats its customers is very influential in the decision to invest in life insurance.

The company-customer relationship is essential in influencing customers' investment decisions. A service provider should know their customer's needs to serve the client correctly, and the desirable quality of service would never be accomplished. As stated by Ahmadi (2013), life insurance companies' staff and agents should offer individual attention to clients while resolving their samples so that they may feel essential. Understanding customer needs and providing them with service accordingly will ensure a decent quality of service and a healthy relationship between company and customer.

Table 8 summarises the investment decision on life insurance policy among public school teachers regarding premium offered, company image, service quality, satisfaction level, and company-client relationship. It is also revealed in the table that among the five (5) factors that influence the investment decision, the factor that has the highest response mean of 3.37 was company image which has a qualitative interpretation of "very highly influential" and is described as "strongly agree."

However, the factor premium offered shows that the respondents only "agree" at this level, which corresponds to a qualitative interpretation of "strongly agree." Overall, the grand mean resulted in 3.25, which is described as "strongly agree" and interpreted as a "very highly influential" factor in the investment decision of the respondents.

Table 8 – Summary Table on the Factors Influencing Investment Decision of Life Insurance Policy among Teachers

Factors	Mean	SD	Verbal Description	Qualitative Interpretation
1. Premium Offered	3.03	0.78	Agree	Highly Influential
2. Company Image	3.37	0.69	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential
3. Service Quality	3.27	0.66	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential
4. Satisfaction Level	3.31	0.66	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential
5. Company - Client Relationship	3.30	0.67	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential
Grand Mean	3.25	0.69	Strongly Agree	Very Highly Influential

Furthermore, Sidhardha & Sumanth (2017) investigated the elements that influence a typical customer's decision to purchase an insurance policy from a specific insurance firm. They even created phases to help customers improve their techniques. As a result, she concluded that consumers had a favorable opinion of life insurance products. A positive mindset has been formed for investing patterns, insurance plans, and an understanding of the benefits of life insurance products, such as marketing.

4.4 Relationship of investment decision factors when grouped with the demographic profile

Table 9 shows the ANOVA result of the influence of investment decisions when grouped according to age. Age generally does not statistically differ except for satisfaction level and company-client relationship based on the decision rule with a p-value of 0.014 and 0.046, respectively. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected because the significance level provided is greater than 0.05, implying that respondents' investment decisions on satisfaction level and company-client relationship are influenced by their age.

Table 9. ANOVA Result of influence of investment decision factors when grouped according to age

Dependent Variables	SS	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Premium Offered	9.769	0.391	1.041	0.440	Accept Ho
Company Image	11.707	0.468	1.411	0.151	Accept Ho
Service Quality	9.873	0.395	1.322	0.200	Accept Ho
Satisfaction Level	13.245	0.530	2.082	0.014	Reject Ho
Company-Client Relationship	14.417	0.577	1.763	0.046	Reject Ho

The research paper conducted by Tiwara & Yadav (2012) concluded that the age of the people differs in their satisfaction level. Generally, the age factor refers to the maturity of the consumer. Generally, elderly consumers are expected to possess greater knowledge and responsibility than younger ones. It plays a major role in deciding life insurance policies. Additionally, as social media immerses, customers have more powerful means to communicate with brands in real-time openly. To maintain a relationship, they need to be willing to respond to the customer, so it will help you reduce customer churn.

Table 10 indicates the results of the analysis that the sex of the respondents does not statistically differ significantly based on the decision rule. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. This is because the significance level provided is higher than the alpha value of 0.05, which indicates that the sex does not significantly differ in the investment decision. Bhanusireesha & Sreelaxmi (2013) conducted a study; it is found that gender quietly does not influence the respondents' investment decisions.

Table 10. ANOVA Result of influence of investment decision factors when grouped according to sex

Dependent Variables	SS	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Premium Offered	1.118	1.118	3.018	0.087	Accept Ho
Company Image	0.014	0.014	0.037	0.849	Accept Ho
Service Quality	0.570	0.570	1.736	0.192	Accept Ho
Satisfaction Level	0.129	0.129	0.368	0.546	Accept Ho
Company-Client Relationship	0.089	0.089	0.214	0.645	Accept Ho

Table 11 indicates the result of the analysis that the rank/position of the respondents does not statistically differ significantly based on the decision rule. Thus, null hypothesis 1 was accepted. This is because the significance level given is greater than the alpha value of 0.05, implying that the influencing factors do not significantly differ when grouped by their rank position. Is it because the teachers have a stable income, whether their rank position is, as long as they want to avail or to invest in life insurances then they can avail.

Table 11. ANOVA Result of influence of investment decision factors when grouped according to rank/position

Dependent Variables	SS	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Premium Offered	1.597	0.200	0.496	0.855	<i>Accept Ho</i>
Company Image	3.109	0.389	1.030	0.423	<i>Accept Ho</i>
Service Quality	2.803	0.350	1.064	0.399	<i>Accept Ho</i>
Satisfaction Level	4.269	0.534	1.637	0.132	<i>Accept Ho</i>
Company-Client Relationship	4.826	0.603	1.550	0.158	<i>Accept Ho</i>

Badunenkeno (2009) conducted surveys in Germany and the Netherlands and concluded that the position of a teacher seems to have no significant influence on the investment decision of the customers. He added that though occupation significantly influences investment, the rank/position does not affect their investment choice. Since consumers' source of income is determined by their occupation. However, because the respondents have a stable income, insurance payment would not be a problem.

As shown in table 12, the result of the analysis of the civil status of the respondents indicates that there is no significant difference statistically based on the decision rule. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. Thus, the significance level provided is greater than the alpha value of 0.05, which implies that the civil status as a profile variable does not significantly differ in the degree of insurance investment decision influencing factors.

It is found that civil status is quietly not influencing the investment decisions of the respondents. The perceptions and attitudes of the person differ over time because the status of the customers might make the person more responsible and mature Berggren (2010).

Table 12. ANOVA Result of influence of investment decision factors when grouped according to civil status

Dependent Variables	SS	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Premium Offered	0.195	0.098	0.252	0.778	<i>Accept Ho</i>
Company Image	1.075	0.537	1.437	0.245	<i>Accept Ho</i>
Service Quality	0.238	0.119	0.352	0.704	<i>Accept Ho</i>
Satisfaction Level	0.191	0.096	0.268	0.765	<i>Accept Ho</i>
Company-Client Relationship	0.317	0.159	0.378	0.687	<i>Accept Ho</i>

Table 13 indicates the result of the analysis that the degree of influence of investment decisions in life insurance of the respondents does not statistically differ significantly based on the decision rule. Thus, the null hypothesis was accepted. This is because the significance level provided is higher than the alpha value of 0.05, which implies that the respondents' years of service as profile do not significantly differ in the influencing factors.

Table 13. ANOVA Result of influence of investment decision factors when grouped according to years in service

Dependent Variables	SS	MS	F	p-value	Decision
Premium Offered	8.917	0.425	1.170	0.314	<i>Accept Ho</i>
Company Image	9.452	0.450	1.287	0.227	<i>Accept Ho</i>
Service Quality	7.733	0.368	1.162	0.322	<i>Accept Ho</i>
Satisfaction Level	7.676	0.366	1.069	0.408	<i>Accept Ho</i>
Company-Client Relationship	11.572	0.551	1.545	0.103	<i>Accept Ho</i>

According to Kenton (2018) which states that, in the competitive world, companies need to provide better customer services and spread more awareness and new and innovative products. The future growth of this industry will be determined by how well insurers meet their customers' expectations and can change consumers' opinions, and keep them informed of insurable risks.

V. CONCLUSION

The majority of the teacher-respondents were females who are still in the age bracket of 24-30 years old but are already married and are new to the education field. The respondents' most preferred type of life insurance policy is whole life insurance, with 48 (65%) of the total number of respondents. It is concluded that company image, service quality, satisfaction level, and company-client relationship play a vital part in contributing to the respondents' investment decisions. Although the premium offered had the lowest response, it is still rated as "agree" and interpreted as "very influential." The grand mean of the influencing factors was 3.25, which is described as "strongly agree," gaining a qualitative interpretation of "very highly influential." This means that all five (5) factors mentioned are the key factors that contributed to the investment decision of the respondents toward a life insurance policy. Based on the analysis of variance, there was no significant difference between the degree of influence of the factors in life insurance policy investment decisions when grouped by their profile variables.

VI. RECOMMENDATION

In a present competitive world, customer satisfaction has become an important aspect of retaining the customers to grow and survive. Customer service is the critical success factor, and through their best services, private insurers can reposition and differentiate themselves from life insurance.

The result of this conducted study will provide the needed knowledge about the possible ways in which the life insurance sectors can increase their investments. Also, this may be used as a basis for other insurance sectors to develop strategies to go beyond the other companies. To achieve greater insurance penetration, the better competition has to be intensified by both the sectors, and they should come up with new innovative products to offer a greater variety of choices to the customers and also make improvements in the quality of services and sell products through appropriate distribution channel to a win-win situation for both the parties. Insurance companies should devise policies that provide effective risk coverage rather than focus on tax benefits and encourage them to invest long-term in insurance (see appendix A). As for the school administrators, especially in Claver District, financial literacy in life insurance investment should be conducted to further the teachers' knowledge. This may be conducted by linking with private insurance companies and the local government unit to help the teachers manage their expenses and secure their future.

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Appendix A

INVESTMENT DECISION ON LIFE INSURANCE POLICY

Rationale:

Nowadays, we experienced rapid technological change, not just in our country but worldwide. That is why insurance sectors should use the technology, so they do not be left behind. The changes in our technology are unpredictable, and it changes constantly. This affects the competitiveness and survival of the business and the customers. This research seeks to determine the possible strategies to support the insurance companies to increase

investments to help not just the customers and insurance companies but also the general public about what life insurance is and what it does.

Objectives:

The experts use the top strategies and online insurance marketing ideas to attract new policyholders, differentiate your brand, and retain existing policyholders are included below. Consumers today are accustomed to instantaneous, smart, and seamless buying experiences. Policyholders want the same simple approach when purchasing insurance as when purchasing new shoes on Amazon. The techniques and ideas that follow are intended to address those concerns. (McLeod,2018)

Doctor up your Insurance Website	Your website is typically the initial point of contact for policyholders with your firm. If they do not connect with what they see within 10 seconds of landing on a webpage, they will move to another provider. Thus, your website needs to be fast, it needs to be secure, and it needs to be mobile-friendly. Although having a website prevents you from talking to the customers personally, it provides the customers less hassle from going to the actual company and waiting to be entertained.
Invest in SEO	You must engage in search engine optimization (SEO) if you want your company to appear on search engines like Google. In order to interact with your website, policyholders have to be able to find you.
Create a Blog	You should start a blog. Blogs not only assist drive visitors to your website, but they also establish your authority on issues, build trust, and change you from an insurance company to a comprehensive insurance resource. Consumers conducting product and service research rely heavily on blog articles. You can provide the needed information about your company and your products to the general public.
Communicate your Brand through Video Marketing	Video marketing is the thing. Using video marketing explains life insurance and saves everyone's time since reading is more time-consuming than visual presentation.
Highlight Differences in Content	Display your awards on the front page of your website. Do you also have plenty of glowing testimonials? Show them off. Is your group the most compassionate in the metro? Post videos to back it up. Determine your target market's pain points and take proactive steps to address them. Consumers may determine whether you are a dependable and trustworthy firm to invest in.
Be Active on Social Media	A whopping 93 percent of insurance agencies report they have some sort of social marketing effort in place. Because of this strategy, you can provide services faster.
Create and Use Email Marketing Newsletters	Someone is taking your position if you do not communicate with your policyholders regularly. Email marketing is a terrific approach to staying top-of-mind with policyholders, reinforcing your brand, and keeping them informed about new and critical developments. Consumers nowadays are research-obsessed, so giving them the information they want is a certain way to hold their attention.

Conclusion

Today the different kinds of diseases are rapidly increasing due to climate change and unhealthy lifestyles, and the demand for life insurance is also increasing. As years passed, our technology was getting advanced. That is why the insurance sector should use advanced technology to keep pace with other sectors. By applying these strategies, the insurance company gives the people in the community easy access to know your company. Customers will have no difficulty coming to the company or the office as the agents can now update them about their insurance investments by posting them online or through emails.

In today's cut-throat competition, life insurance companies may use the technology to provide better customer services and spread more awareness and new and innovative products so that every individual may avail the benefits of insurance and protect their lives against future uncertainties.